

Influence of Extrinsic and Intrinsic Motivation on Pupils Academic Performance in Mathematics

Onyekwere Nonye Adamma

Department of Educational Psychology, Alvan Ikoku University of Education,
Owerri Imo State, Nigeria, *nonyeonyekere2013@gmail.com*

Okoro Pauline Ekwutosim

Department of Educational Psychology, Federal College of Education Eha-Amufu, Enugu State, Nigeria,
okoropauline1@gmail.com

Eugene Chukwuemeka Unamba *

Department of Primary Education Studies, Alvan Ikoku University of Education, Owerri Imo State, Nigeria,
*corresponding author, *unambaec@yahoo.com*

Article Info

Article history:

Received April 30th, 2018

Revised June 07th, 2018

Accepted June 07th, 2018

Keywords:

Extrinsic and intrinsic motivation, academic performance, mathematics

ABSTRACT

The study investigated influence of extrinsic and intrinsic motivation on pupils' academic performance in mathematics. Based on the purpose of the study two hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of all 3056 primary six pupils in Owerri Education zone of Imo State. A Sample size of 200 primary six pupils was selected for the study. Simple random sampling technique was used in selecting four schools out of the nine schools. The instruments used for data collection was Academic Motivation Scale and Mathematics achievement Test. The validity was determined by two experts in measurement and evaluation and one expert in mathematics education. The instruments have reliability co-efficient of 0.89 and 0.92 determined using tests-retest method. Data generated was analyzed with the aid SPSS version. Inferential statistics of T-test and Pearson product moment correlation were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study concludes that motivation improves academic performance of the pupils and there is gender difference in motivation type and academic performance.

Copyright © 2018 by the authors; licensee Department of Mathematics Education, University of Singaperbangsa Karawang. All rights reserved.

This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the CC BY-SA license. (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0>)

INTRODUCTION

Globally, there has been an increasing concern in the education sector on how to ensure that students learn optimally at school and achieve academic excellence in their academic pursuit. In Nigeria, there has been a nationwide cry on the fallen standards of education and poor performance of pupils in mathematics. Various factors have been identified for poor academic achievement among students and these include poor study habit, laziness, ineffective classroom instructions, and inadequate provision of instructional material and lack of motivation (Akpan, 2000).

Motivating students to learn in school is a topic of great concern for educationist today and motivating students so that they can succeed in school is one of the greatest

challenges of this century (Awan, Noureen & Nas, 2011). Getting students to learn and sustaining their interest in what they are learning therefore should be the sole objective of teachers in the classroom. Motivation is a significantly important factor for academic learning and achievement (Elliot & Dweck, 2005). Moula (2010) observes that motivation is one of the factors that contribute to academic success; that parents and educators should strive to understand the importance of promoting and encouraging academic motivation early in life. Feldman (2005) refers to motivation as factors that direct and energize the behaviour of humans and other organisms, while Wood (2002) sees motivation as a process that initiates, directs, and sustains behaviours to satisfy physiological or psychological needs. Motivation is also seen as what gets one going, keeps one going, and determines where one is going (Slarin, 2006). According to Self-determination theory (Ryan & Deci, 2000) there are two types of motivation i.e. extrinsic motivation and intrinsic motivation.

Intrinsic motivation is an inner force that motivates students to engage in academic activities, because they are interested in learning and they enjoy the learning process as well (Schiefele, 1991). Harter (1978) explained that intrinsic motivation is the true drive in human nature, which drives individuals to search for and to face new challenges. Their abilities are put to the test and they are eager to learn even when there are no external rewards to be won. Students with learning goals of seeking understanding for mastery of science content and skills are said to be intrinsically motivated (Cavallo, Rozman, Blinkenstaff, & Walker, 2003).

Csikszentmihalyi and Nakamura (1989) stated that intrinsically motivated individuals possess the following characteristics: They engage in both mental and physical activities holistically, they remain highly focused throughout these activities with clearly defined goals, they are self-critical, they self-reflect on their own actions realistically, and they are usually relaxed and not afraid to fail during learning. A research study done by Stipek (1988) concluded that intrinsically motivated students learn independently and always choose to do challenging tasks. They persevere to complete the tasks they have undertaken. They integrate the knowledge acquired in school with their experiences gained from outside school. They often ask questions to broaden their knowledge and learn regardless of any external push factors or help from teachers, and they take pride in their work and express positive emotions during the learning process. Highly intrinsically motivated students are able to learn new concepts successfully and show better understanding of the subject matter (Stipek, 1988). Unlike intrinsic motivation; extrinsic motivation drives students to engage in academic tasks for external reasons.

Extrinsic motivators include parental expectations, expectations of other trusted role models, earning potential to enroll in a course later and good grades. According to Benabou and Tirole (2003), extrinsic motivation promotes effort and performance with rewards serving as positive reinforces for the desired behavior. Extrinsic motivation typically produces immediate results and requires less effort in comparison to intrinsic motivation (Ryan & Deci, 2000). The down side of it is that extrinsic motivators can often distract students from true independent learning. Another problem with extrinsic motivators is that they typically do not work over the long term. Once, the rewards are removed, students lose their motivation (DeLong & Winter, 2002). As extrinsically motivated, students tend to focus on earning higher grades and obtaining rewards, Biehler and Snowman (1990) believed that extrinsic motivational factors can diminish students' intrinsic motivation. Such observation has also been reported by Bain (2004) who concluded that extrinsic rewards have negative impacts on intrinsic motivation. Gender differences in the motivation to learn science has attracted much attention during the last

decade (Eccles & Blumenfield, 1985; Greene & DeBacker, 2004; Greenfield, 1998; Morrell & Lederman, 1998).

Evidence accumulated thus far on gender differences in motivation is inconclusive. While many studies (Anderman & Anderman, 1999; Ayub, 2010; Lai, Chan, & Wong, 2006; Meece & Holt, 1993) reported that there are gender differences in extrinsic and intrinsic motivation between male and female students, studies by Rusillo and Arias (2004) and Glynn et al. (2009) reported otherwise. Whereas on academic performance Schiefele, Krapp, and Winteler (1992) strongly suggests that, “male students’ performance accords their interest level more than is the case for female students”. In particular, “female students’ academic performance is less associated with their interests than male students’ academic performance” (Schiefele, Krapp, & Winteler, 1992).

Numerous studies suggested that from childhood through adolescence, across varied populations, those with higher academic intrinsic motivation have been found to be more competent in school, generally evidencing significantly greater academic achievement, more positive perceptions of their academic competency, lower academic anxiety, and less extrinsic motivation (Gottfried, A.W., Gottfried, Cook, & Morris, 2005). Johnson (1996), Broussard and Garrison (2004), Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2006), and Sandra (2002) found significant relationship between academic performance and motivation. Similarly, Johnson (1996) found that academic achievement is highly correlated with student’s motivation. However, Bank and Finlapson (1980) found that successful students were found to have significantly higher motivation for achievement than unsuccessful students did.

In the light of above studies, the main objective of the present study was to examine the relationship between extrinsic and intrinsic motivation on academic performance of pupils in mathematics. Furthermore, this study explores gender difference on the variable of extrinsic motivations, and intrinsic motivation.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the relationship between extrinsic and intrinsic motivation on academic performance of pupils in mathematics. Specifically it seeks to examine, (1) Relationship between extrinsic motivation on academic performance of pupils in mathematics; (2) Relationship between intrinsic motivation on academic performance of pupils in mathematics; and (3) Whether gender difference will exist on extrinsic and intrinsic motivation.

Hypotheses

Ho₁; What is the relationship between extrinsic and intrinsic motivation on academic performance of pupils in mathematics.

Ho₂; What is the relationship between extrinsic and intrinsic motivation on academic performance of pupils in mathematics

Ho₃; There is no significant difference between male and female pupils scores on extrinsic and intrinsic motivation.

METHOD

The study adopted a descriptive survey design in carrying out the study on influence of extrinsic and intrinsic motivation on pupils’ academic achievement in mathematics. The population comprised of all 3,056 primary six pupils in Owerri Municipal Council Area of

Imo-State. A sample size of 200 primary six pupils was selected for the study using simple random sampling technique in selecting two schools. In the selected schools purposive sampling technique was used to select classes that have more than three streams. The age range is between 18-21 years. The instruments used for data collection were *Academic Motivation Scale (AMS)*. The AMS consists of 28 items and the second was Achievement Test on Mathematics (MAT). It consists of 20 multiple choice test items with four options (A- D). The face and content validity of the instrument was done by experts in mathematics education and one expert in measurement and evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was established using test re test method which yields reliability coefficient of 0.89 and 0.92 respectively.

The questionnaire was administered to respondents and they completed the questionnaire. After collection of data of the questionnaire, Academic Motivation Scale (Vallerand, 1992) was scored according to the instructions given in the manual. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and t-test were applied through Statistical Package for Social Sciences, 13 versions was used to determine the relationship.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

H₀₁; What is the relationship between extrinsic and intrinsic motivation on academic performance of pupils in mathematics.

H₀₂; There is no significant difference between male and female pupils scores on extrinsic and intrinsic motivation.

Table 1. Correlation between Motivation and Academic Performance

	Grade Point	Significance
Academic Motivation	.563**	.000

Note. Shows correlation between academic motivation and academic performance significant at**p=.000

Table 2 t- test Gender Difference on Academic Motivation and Academic Performance

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Std Dev	t	df	Sig
Academic Motivation	Female	200	131.13	6.386	4.324	198	.000
	Male	200	126.91	7.379			

Note. Verifies Significant difference was found between male and female (t= 4.324, df =198, p<.05) on the variable of academic motivation and academic performance.

The result of testing the first hypothesis, which evaluates the correlation between motivation and academic performance, is found to be significant (r =.563; n=200). These findings are consistent with previous literature. For example, Johnson (1996), Broussard and Garrison (2004), Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2006), and Sandra (2002) found significant relationship between academic performance and motivation. Similarly, Johnson (1996)

found that academic achievement is highly correlated with student's motivation. However, Bank and Finlapson (1980) found that successful students were found to have significantly higher motivation for achievement than unsuccessful students did.

Motivation types also effects on the performance of the students. Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation affects on the achievements and goals of the students performance. According to Husman and Lens (1999), highly intrinsically motivated students can simultaneously be extrinsic in terms of future goal orientations. Furthermore, students who are intrinsically motivated persist longer, conquer more challenges, and demonstrate accomplishments in their academic endeavors than those who are extrinsically motivated (Pintrich & Garcia, 1991). Extrinsically motivated students tend to focus on earning higher grades, obtaining rewards and acceptance from peers. Researchers, for example, Biehler & Snowman, (1990) believe that extrinsic motivational factors diminish students' intrinsic motivation. Students' extrinsic motivational factors combined with positive future goals can actually facilitate their present value and intrinsic motivation (Van Calster, Lens, & Nuttin, 1987).

According to the results, there is gender difference on the variable of extrinsic and intrinsic motivation on academic performance ($t=4.324, p <.05$). These findings which are consistent with Chee, Pino and Smith (2005) indicated that female college students are more likely to have higher academic ethics than male students, which are characterized by higher academic attainment. Furthermore, findings of the study suggests that females were intrinsically motivated than males. In contrast, males were more extrinsically motivated than females. The possible explanations of these findings are that males are expected to be the main breadwinner of the family in our society. For females, academic performance and motivation is based on self-exploration and internal satisfaction. This is the main reason that males are extrinsically motivated as compare to females.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, findings of the study illustrates that motivation improves academic performance of the students. These findings suggests that when teachers are caring and supportive and emphasize the teaching learning process over the performance outcomes, and when they give feedback, children tend to be motivated to achieve and to expect success (Daniels, Kalkman, & McCombs, 2001). In addition, there is gender difference in motivation type and academic performance.

The findings suggest that teachers should explore and use this strategy to make students more determined and efficacious to learn mathematics. Teachers should also attempt to link mathematics concepts to pupils' experiences, so that they can realize the relevance of what they learn to their everyday lives, thus making learning more meaningful and relevant.

REFERENCES

- Akpan, I. D. (2000). Single Parenting and Social Adjustment of Adolescent Students. *University of Uyo Journal of Women Academics (UJOWACS)*. 1(1), 164 – 125.
- Anderman, L. H. (1999). Classroom goal orientation, school belonging and social goals as predictors of students' positive and negative affect following the transition to middle school. *Journal of Research and Development in Education*, 32, 89-103.

- Awan, R., Noureen, G., Naz, A. (2011). A Study of Relationship between Achievement Motivation, Self concept and Achievement in English and Mathematics at Secondary level. *International Education Studies*, 4(3), 72 – 78.
- Ayub, N. (2010). Effect of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation on academic performance. In K. College of Business Management (Ed.), *Pakistan Business Review*. Retrieved March 1, 2011, from <http://www.jobm.edu.pk/PBR/PBR1007363The%20Effect%20of%20Intrinsic%20and%20Extrinsic%20Motivation%20revise.pdf>.
- Bain, K. (2004). *What the best college teachers do*. Harvard University Press.
- Bank, C. and Finlapson, W. (1980). *Successful Motivation of Students in Academic Activities* in McClelland, D.C. Appleton-Century-Crafts.
- Benabou, R., & Tirole, J. (2003). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. *Review of Economic Studies*, 70, 489-520.
- Biehler, R. F., & Snowman, J. (1990). *Psychology applied to teaching* (6th ed.). Boston: Houghton Mifflin.
- Broussard, S. C. & Garrison, M.E. (2004). The relationship between classroom motivation and academic achievement in elementary school-aged children. *Family Consumer Science Research Journal*, 33(2), 106-120.
- Cavallo, A. M. L., Rozman, M., Blinkenstaff, J., & Walker, N. (2003). Students' learning approaches, reasoning abilities, motivational goals and epistemological beliefs in differing college science courses. *Journal of College Science Teaching*, 33, 18-23.
- Chee, K.H., N.W. Pino, and W.L. Smith. 2005. Gender differences in the academic ethic and academic achievement. *College Student Journal* 39, no. 3: 604-19.
- Csikszentmihalyi, M., & Nakamura, J. (1989). The dynamics of intrinsic motivation: A study of adolescents. In C. Ames, & R. Ames (Eds.), *Research on motivation in education: Goals and cognitions* (Vol. 3, pp. 45-72). San Diego: Academic Press.
- Daniels, D.H., Kalkman, D.L. & Mc Combs, B.L. (2001) Young children's perspectives on learning and teacher practices in different classroom contexts: implications for motivation, *Early Education & Development*, 12 (2), 253-273.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behavior. *New York: Plenum*.
- Deci, E.L. (1975). *Intrinsic motivation*. New York: Plenum Press.
- Deci, E.L., & Ryan, R.M. (1991). A motivational approach to self: Integration in personality. In R.A. Dienstbier (Ed.), *Nebraska symposium on motivation: Perspectives on motivation* (Vol. 38, pp. 237-288). Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press.
- DeLong, M., & Winter, D. (2002). Strategies for motivating students. *Learning to teach and teaching to learn mathematics: Resources for professional development* (pp.159-168). Washington, D. C.: Mathematical Association of America.
- Eccles, J., & Blumenfield, P. C. (1985). Classroom experiences and student's gender: Are the differences and does it matter? In L.C. Wilkenson, & C. B. Marrett (Eds.), *Gender influences in classroom interaction*. Orlando, F. L.: Academic.
- Elliott, A.J., & Dweck, C.S. (2005). *Handbook of competence and motivation*. New York: Guilford Press.
- Feldman, R. S. (2005). *Understanding Psychology 7th E*. New York: McGraw Hill Higher Education.
- Glynn, S. M., Taasobshirazi, G., & Brickman, P. (2009). Science motivation questionnaire: Construct validation with no science majors. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 46(2), 127-146.

- Gottfried, A.W. (1985). Measures of socioeconomic status in child development research: Data and recommendations. *Merrill-Palmer Quarterly*, 31, 85-92.
- Gottfried, A.W., Gottfried, A.E., Cook, C., & Morris, P. (2005). Educational characteristics of adolescents with gifted academic intrinsic motivation: A longitudinal study from school entry through early adulthood. *Gifted Child Quarterly*, 49, 172-186.
- Greene, B. A., & DeBacker, T. K. (2004). Gender and orientations toward the future: Links to motivation. *Educational Psychology Review*, 16, 91-120.
- Greenfield, T. A. (1998). Gender and grade level differences in science interest and participation. *Science Education*, 81(3), 259-276.
- Harter, S. (1978). Effectance motivation reconsidered: Toward a developmental model. *Human Development*, 21, 34-64
- Harter, S. (1981). A new self-report Scale of Intrinsic versus Extrinsic Orientation in the Classroom: Motivational and informational components. *Developmental Psychology*, 17, 300-312.
- Husman, J., & Lens, W. (1999). *The role of the future in student motivation*. *Educational Psychologist*, 34(2), 113-125.
- Johnson, J. O. (1996). *Child Psychology*. Wusen Press Limited. Calabar, Nigeria.
- Lai, P. Y., Chan, K. W., & Wong, K. Y. (2006). A study of intrinsic motivation, achievement goals and study strategies of Hong Kong Chinese secondary students. Paper presented at *The Annual Conference of the Australian Association for Research in Education*, Adelaide, Australia.
- Meece, J.L. & Holt, K. (1993). A pattern analysis of students' achievement goals. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 85, 582-590.
- Morrell, P. D., & Lederman, N. G. (1998). Students' attitudes toward school and classroom science: Are they independent? *School Science and Mathematics*, 98, 76-82.
- Muola, J. M. (2010). A Study of the Relationship between Academic Achievement Motivation and Home Environment among Standard Eight Pupils. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 5(5), 213-217.
- Pintrich, P. R. & Garcia, T. (1991). Student goal orientation and self-regulated learning in the college classroom. In M. L. Maehr & P. R. Pintrich (Eds.), *Advances in motivation and achievement: Goals and self-regulatory processes* (Vol. 7, pp. 371-402). Greenwich, CT: JAI press.
- Rusillo, M. T. C., & Arias, P. F. C. (2004). Gender differences in academic motivation of secondary school children. *Electronic Journal of Research in Educational Psychology and Psychopedagogy*. Retrieved August 1, 2011, from http://www.investigacion-psicopedagogica.org/revista/articulos/3/english/art_3_31.pdf
- Ryan, R.M., & Deci, E.L. (2000). When rewards compete with nature: The understanding of intrinsic motivation and self regulation. pp14-54
- Sandra, D. (2002). Mathematics and science achievement: effects of motivation, interest and academic engagement. *Journal of Educational Research*, 95(6), 323-332.
- Schiefele, U. (1991). Interest, learning and motivation. *Educational Psychologist*, 26(3&4), 299-323.
- Schiefele, U., Krapp, A., & Winteler, A. (1992). Interest as a predictor of academic achievement: A meta-analysis of research. The role of interest in learning and development (pp. 183-212). Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum
- Skaalvik, E. M., Skaalvik, S. (2006). Self-concept and self-efficacy in Mathematics: Relation with Mathematics motivation and achievement. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Learning Sciences*, Bloomington, Indiana.

- Slavin, D. (2006). *The Educational Psychology: Theory into Practice*. Eaglewood Cliff, N. J.: Prentice Hall.
- Stipek, D. J. (1988). *Motivation to learn: From theory to practice* (2nd ed.). Massachusetts: Allyn and Bacon.
- Uguroglu, M. E., & Walberg, H.J. (1979), Motivation and achievement: A quantitative synthesis. *American Educational Research Journal*, 16, 375-389
- Vallerand, R.J., Pelletier, L.G., Blais, M.R, Briere, N.M., Senecal, C., & Vallieres, E.F. (1992). The academic motivation scale: a measure of intrinsic, extrinsic, and amotivation in education. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 52, 1003-1017.
- Van Calster, K., Lens, W., & Nuttin, J. (1987). Affective attitude toward the personal future: Impact on motivation in high school boys. *American Journal of Psychology*, 100, 1-13.

Pengaruh Motivasi Ekstrinsik dan Intrinsik Terhadap Performa Akademik Matematika Siswa

Onyekwere Nonye Adamma

Program Studi Psikologi Pendidikan, Universitas Pendidikan Alvan Ikoku,
Owerri Imo State, Nigeria, *nonyeonyekere2013@gmail.com*

Okoro Pauline Ekwutosim

Program Studi Psikologi Pendidikan, Sekolah Tinggi Federal Eha-Amufu, Enugu State, Nigeria,
okoropauline1@gmail.com

Eugene Chukwuemeka Unamba*

Program Studi Pendidikan Dasar, Universitas Pendidikan Alvan Ikoku, Owerri Imo State, Nigeria,
*penulis korespondensi, *unambaec@yahoo.com*

ABSTRAK

Penelitian ini mengkaji pengaruh motivasi ekstrinsik dan intrinsik pada performa akademik matematika siswa. Penelitian ini berdasarkan dua hipotesis penelitian. Penelitian ini menggunakan desain penelitian deskriptif. Populasi penelitian terdiri dari 3056 siswa sekolah dasar di wilayah Owerri, Imo State. Ukuran Sampel dari 200 siswa utama enam siswa dipilih untuk penelitian. Teknik sampling acak sederhana digunakan dalam memilih empat sekolah dari sembilan sekolah. Instrumen yang digunakan untuk pengumpulan data adalah Skala Motivasi Akademik dan Tes Prestasi Matematika. Validitas ditentukan oleh dua ahli dalam pengukuran dan evaluasi dan satu ahli dalam pendidikan matematika. Instrumen memiliki koefisien reabilitas 0,89 dan 0,92 ditentukan menggunakan metode test-retest. Data yang dihasilkan dianalisis dengan bantuan versi SPSS. Statistik inferensial dari t-test dan korelasi product Moment Person Pearson digunakan untuk menguji hipotesis pada tingkat signifikansi 0,05. Studi ini menyimpulkan bahwa motivasi meningkatkan kinerja akademik siswa dan ada perbedaan jenis kelamin dalam jenis motivasi dan kinerja akademik.

Kata kunci: Motivasi ekstrinsik dan intrinsik, performa akademik, matematika

Diterima 30 April 2018

Direvisi 07 Juni 2018

Disetujui 07 Juni 2018